

DESIGNERS OUT OF DEMAND? NEIGHBOURHOODS, ORGANIZED COMMUNITIES, LOCAL DEVELOPMENT AND 'ORDINARY' PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is above all, to discuss the role of politic and government intervention as driver of co-creation, co-design and participatory approaches among non-design communities in the Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela. The paper briefly presents a context description of design and participation in Venezuela and then, provides a literature review based on European and North American views of creative communities and, the relationship of design and politics. The law of community council decreed in 2009 in Venezuela is presented. Two case studies are introduced, illustrating the achievements of organized communities in the context of the participatory democracy drive by the presidency of Hugo Chávez Firías. The paper addresses the role of 'ordinary' people as designers; and determines the benefit of designer's participation in community building and neighbourhood development.

Keywords: creative communities, social design, community design, urban development

INTRODUCTION

Since the last two decades design seems to be the new baby born in Venezuela. There is a great amount of training schools and institutions established in the country since early 1980. They merely focus on graphic design, visual communication and marketing design, making it the most popular fields of studies among young Venezuelans. Venezuela under the digital revolution of visual communication and graphic design for gaining financial profit emerged on an array

of visible ways. It includes the design and production of stands and objects for shops and fairs, and the entire visual communication for local companies. Generally, these design institutions are private, making it difficult for people of low economical resources to access them. Many private design institutions also offer industrial design and interior design. However, the Central University of Venezuela founded in 1721 gives a longer history of education in the area of visual arts, fine arts and architecture.

The current education of industrial design in Venezuela seems to deal with traditional aspects of product design such as ergonomics, function, aesthetics, efficiency, cost, and to a certain extent, product design education also relates to the sociological and psychological aspects derived from each object. In Venezuela, as in most of the countries where the education of design takes three years, product design is taught using traditional views on design. In this sense, design (graphic, interior and industrial) aims to mainly serve the private sector and the production process. However, the only university that offers master's degree in industrial design focused on the technical aspects of products, leaving behind research and design on services, systems and socially oriented. The design practice in Venezuela seems to be often focusing on design-centred approach, instead of user-centred approach where the designer studies real users and tries to understand them before making design commitments.

Design, at least in Europe and the USA, has appropriated tools and approaches from the human and social sciences. The design methodology consists of empirical research which is evaluated and

developed into design ideas in teams. (Koskinen, 2003). They focus on real users and real situations, and utilize ethnographic methods from anthropology that have been adapted and adopted by human-centred design practice. These methods focus on objective observation of behaviour, of what people say and do; and, they serve to identify people's abilities, lifestyle and preferences as they relate to design. (ibid.) However, knowledge on subjective phenomena was regarded to be more useful because it helps designers to understand people's experiences. (ibid).

Currently, designers also often participate in the lives of the people they study; it provides them a full understanding of users' world and life context. Within the landscape of participatory design, the notions of co-creation and co-design emerged. Co-creation refers to "any act of collective creativity, i.e., creativity that is shared by two or more people. Co-creation is a very broad term with applications ranging from the physical to the metaphysical and from the material to the spiritual" ... "Co-design refers to the creativity of designers and people not trained in design working together in the design development process. Thus, co-design is a specific instance of co-creation". (Sanders et al 2008, p. 2). These new notions in design gave birth to new tools that focus on what people make – "how they construct their world for themselves in their dreams, imaginations and ruminations of various sorts" (in Koskinen, 2003 p. 60). The methods are called "generative tools or maketools" which is a new language for co-designing. (Sanders, 2000). Thus, several types of tools have emerged including "emotional toolkits" and "cognitive toolkits" for instance. (Sandres et al, 1999).

Design research contributes to the discussion and formation of different topics of concern that evolve at different pace in various parts of the world. While in some countries design research has advanced enormously, others seem to concentrate on the traditional view and scope of design, and design research, as it is the case in Venezuela. Moreover, neighbourhood, community and city development have become a matter of growing interest in Europe and USA in terms of design investigation and design practice throughout the last decades (see e.g. Thackara, 2005; Fuad-Luke, 2009;

Augé 1995; Carmona et. al, 2003; Gehl 2010). One of the challenges of city design deals with the application of participatory design and user-centered design approaches and, in making governments to accept the importance of user involvement in design activities and community development (see Kirkpatrick, 2000). Designing for communities, unlike the more traditional designing of products for companies, involves rather ideas for services and for people that unfold in a specific geographic area. Moreover, the new opportunities of design in the public sector open doors to emerging areas in design that can be explored. According to a survey done by Design Council in United Kingdom the 22% of the complete clients for design businesses are public administration, health and education. There is a "rise in the number of design business doing work for public sector and non-profit clients over the past few years." (Julier, Proc. Nordes 2010, p. 77).

But, what can we learn from the current situation of Venezuela where design is just starting to flourish and, to a certain extent they are living the design process of 1990's where the role of the customer to consumer to user is established? Simultaneously, Venezuela focuses on community and neighbourhood development based on local knowledge, which evolve by politic and government intervention that place participatory approaches and co-creation at the core front of the country's drivers, as the main values and strategies established throughout the presidency of Hugo Chávez Frías. There is an overall gap between the conception and practice of design and, the current political and governmental agenda. When and how these two fully meet will remain under study in the coming years, as the experiment it is just taking shape.

The government implemented in 2005 the law of community service for higher education students which positions individuals, communities and students in an effort to contribute to the transformation and development of the country (see Viña, 2012). However, it might take time for new methods, approaches, tools and methodologies to establish in the design field in Venezuela, especially in the line of participation and co-design and the general thinking of social and sustainable design. On the other side,

'ordinary' people are more or less playing the role of designers in Venezuelan communities due to another government incentive created to support people's capability on decision-making, community formation and social organization. The law of communal councils decreed in 2009 aims to regulate the constitution, organization and operation of communal councils as a call for participation and self-development. Individuals are addressed to get organized, form local communities and communal councils in their neighbourhoods in order to facilitate activities and decisions that can improve their immediate surrounding and everyday life.

The aim of this paper is above all, to discuss the role of politic and government intervention as driver of co-creation, co-design and participatory approaches among non-design communities in the Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela. The paper provides a literature review based on European and North American views of creative communities and, the relationship of design and politics. The law of community council decreed in 2009 in Venezuela is presented. Two case studies are introduced, illustrating the achievements of organized communities in the context of the participatory democracy drive by the presidency of Hugo Chávez Fírías. The paper addresses the role of 'ordinary' people as designers; and determines the benefit of designer's participation in community building and neighbourhood development.

POLITIC AND GOVERNMENT INTERVENTION: ENCOURAGING CREATIVITY AND COMMUNITY ORGANIZATION

Over the last decade Venezuela is in a social and economic transition. The shift is from the capitalist and neoliberal model to the 21st Century socialism. This social model is a revolutionary socialism directly linked to the philosophy and the Marxist economy. The model sustains four axes: the regional democratic development, the economy of equivalence, participatory democracy and thus protagonist and, grassroots organizations. The vision is part of Karl Marx's social dynamic and the class struggle. The country supports independence from capitalism by promoting cultural independency; moral power; love and peace as the basis of socialism; the politics of

liberation; and, the development and growth of the country must be in complete social harmony. The ideology structure of the revolutionary socialism lies in self-management and the idea of creative communities and sustainability, ideology by Ezio Manzini and the Design for Social Innovation towards Sustainability (DESI).

Although the role of design and designers is not mention in the lines of the plan of economic and social development of the nation; design, specially co-design for socio-material interactions, are part of the political agenda of Venezuela. It means that the concept of design as driver of social innovation and sustainability is achievable by any person, whether a professional designer or not. It is fundamental within this work the meaning of 'ordinary' people as designers and drivers of change and development in the personal and socio-economic levels. The premise of this paper is based on Viktor Papanek (1974) statement "all men are designers. All that we do, almost all the time, is design, for design is basic to all human activity – the placing and patterning of any act towards a desired goal constitutes a design process." Also, Herb Simon noted "everyone designs who devises course of action aimed at changing existing situations, into preferred ones." (Simon, 1996). The relation between politics and design is thus relevant, especially when participatory approaches; empowerment and creative communities are promoted by the government as accessible and possible by and for all citizens.

The constitution introduced by President Chávez was approved by Venezuelans in a popular referendum. It preserves rights of previously excluded and minority groups. The emphasis of the new national policy is on social inclusion and promotes participatory democracy through community councils, urban land committees and other local entities. The spotlight of the current change is illuminating low-income areas in cities and rural areas. The process of transformation includes various actors and stakeholders such as grassroots organizations, organized communities; governmental bodies; NGOs, private sector and others. Philine Warnke and Helma Luiten (2006, p.164) illustrate that "a crucial precondition for the successful transition towards a knowledge intensive economy is the ability of all actors of the innovation system to learn and

react to change. As innovation studies have long been pointing out, it is the quality of the whole system of innovation and no longer the excellence of single elements that determines success within a knowledge-based economy." According to Alastair Fuad-Luke (2009) the regeneration of societies "requires inclusion of a wider range of actors and stakeholders in the design *and* decision-making processes. Communities are creative if given the right support and resources to prove it. Designers' potential to assist these communities in realizing new visions is considerable, but it needs bringing to life on the ground." (ibid p.195). Radical redirection and inclusion of different stakeholder seem to be a requirement in the process of a real democracy and in the strategic level of the government.

Worldwide great examples of self-organized and self-developed communities (see Thackara, 2005; Leeuw, 2007) show new structures of civil societies that make powerful ideas, products and services for a real need and, the communities themselves are transforming into sustainable models of innovation. There also is lack of policies, activities, incentives and subsidy that can help creative communities to flourish and practice their democratic right. A great number of research and case studies show and recommend policymakers new organizational forms that can engage and drive creative communities and milieus, these are bottom-up initiatives; social cohesion; sustainable development, and diverse cultural activities, large and small sides among others. (see Leeuw, 2007; Warnke, 2006; Stø and Strandbakken 2006).

According to Tony Fry (2011) the design of cities and 'invention' of a cultural and material economy requires "a radical mind that moves away from the notion of perceptual growth towards a situation in which quantity is displaced by quality (itself redefined, elaborated and culturally infused)." (Ibid. p. 64) He illustrates that the political vision needs to bring together the practical tasks of discussing the performative, material and cultural attribute of what is needed and produced. Thus, production is re-conceptualized becoming more responsible of what is produced, and touching upon environmental concerns to skill and knowledge, and therefore social ecology. Moreover, a variety of 'producer service' incentives

can draw attention to major development such as local food production; local water management; child care: waste management; technical support and maintenance services, renewal energy systems and buildings. Therefore, the reinvention of the city can happen through a new methodological approach enriched by regulations, public policies and subsidy; based on the meta level of moving radically from quantity to quality.

LAW OF COMMUNITY COUNCILS

One of the strategies of President Chavez towards the construction of the 21st Century socialism is neighbourhood self-management. A new law was decreed in Venezuela in 2009: the law of communal councils which aims to regulate the constitution, organization and operation of communal councils as a request for participation. The objective of this law is to include the direct practice of the popular sovereignty and, its relation to different entities of the public power to the formulation, execution, control and evaluation of public policies, plans and projects related to community development. The communal councils, in the constitutional framework of the participatory democracy and protagonist, are petitions for participation, articulation and integration between citizens and different community organizations. They are requests for social and popular movements that allow the organized community to apply the communal administration and direct management of their everyday common environment. This public policy and project oriented attempts to meet the necessities, potential and aspirations of communities. (Ley Orgánica de los Consejos Comunales, 2009)

The law of community councils gives communities more power to co-create their everyday living environment. Chávez promotes the creation of community councils because he believes that ordinary people can transform the social relations of production, building a socialist model based on social and local ownership. However, President Chávez is aware of the challenges within the government itself including corruption, disorganization and lack of responsibility. The president reaffirms in his public talks, the need to give more power to communities and form a new political culture based on citizens' awareness on principles and values of participation,

responsibility, democracy, national identity, free debate of ideas, coordination, cooperation, solidarity, transparency, accountability, honesty, common good, humanity, territoriality, collectivism, effectiveness, efficiency, ethics, social responsibility, social control, freedom, equity, justice, volunteering, social and gender equality in order to establish the socio-political basis of socialism to consolidate the new political, social, cultural and economic model. (Líneas Generales, 2007).

ORGANIZED COMMUNITIES, LOCAL DEVELOPMENT, DESIGN AND CREATIVITY

The law of communal councils decreed in Venezuela defines community as “the core and indivisible space consisting of individuals and families living in a given geographical area, linked by common characteristics and interests, share a history, needs and, they have potential in developing cultural, economic, social and the territorial aspects of the community among others.” (Ley orgánica, 2009 p.4). John Thackara (2009, p.131) says that a community is not a network and illustrates that “a community embodies trust and social capital that develop through time as a result of embodied interaction between people.” Any community shares things in common; it is a requisite for a community to come into existence.

A community can take shape based on the same physical and geographical space or on the same ideals. Communities also share the same culture and thus “a culture can be distinguished by a set of characteristics within a group of people, including thoughts, values, and behaviours (Choi, Lee, Kim, & Jeon, 2005). Moreover, cultures evolve through specific social facts such as religion, politics, rituals, values and language. (Searle, 1995; Bourges-Waldegg & Scrivener, 1998). Culture does not determine individuals’ behaviour but touches upon people’s way of perception, thought and action. Thus, cultures and communities are structures as well as processes obtained through the interaction with the environment and between cultural, political, economical and social models.

Activist communities often look into new ways that can restructure and construct new socio-economic models. Also, alternative design groups sprung all

over the world. They explore the role of simpler lifestyle, which goes against the consumerist society and its diverse negative impact to the environment and societies. For example, the permaculture design founded by Bill Mollison and David Holmgren in mid 1970s; and being developed and adopted by other communities as grassroots localisations like Transition Towns (see Fuad-Luke, 2009, p. 47).

In Henri Poincaré’s (in Manzini, 2007) words creativity “means joining pre-existing elements in new useful combinations”. Ezio Manzini (2007) illustrates a series of active minorities as creative communities.

Throughout the book the term creative communities is referred to radical innovations of local systems (p.14); self-organization and bottom-up innovation (p.147); the spirit that animates them and that animates the situations they have been capable of engendering (p.170); a non-rhetorical view of reality, a positive even cheerful attitude, and an intrinsically entrepreneurial spirit (and courage) (p.10) among others. Creative communities are “invention of new ways of living and doing.” For it to really be a social innovation it must stabilise and consolidate their structure. (Manzini, 2006, p. 8). In the next sections I describe the area *23 de Enero* which is the neighbourhood where the case studies evolve.

COMMUNITIES IN 23 DE ENERO, CARACAS

The district *23 de Enero* (January 23) situated in Caracas has become through years a reference of popular resistance and social struggle. The place is an urbanization built by the dictator Marcos Perez Jimenez at the end of 1950s and which name was 2 de Diciembre (December 2), day which the dictator used to inaugurate his big architectural projects. Before the urbanization was built the land was the first low-income housing area in Caracas. People came from the countryside to look for the capital’s development and benefit. The slum disappeared by order of Perez Jiménez and the construction of an urbanization inspired by the urban and architectural theories of Le Corbusier generated 9.176 apartments in a total of 38 super buildings; also local services were built such as schools, markets, kindergartens, and so on. The dictator Perez Jiménez was defeated in January 23rd of 1.958, by then many apartments were still empty. A disorganized appropriation of the

apartments took place, and most of them were invaded. This is how started the history of rebellion adopted by the district *23 de Enero*. Through years the existing green areas of the urbanization became slums, modest houses and living area for low-income people. This brought a significant raise in the demography of the *23 de Enero* and the centre and west side of the capital.

Since the defeat of dictator Perez Jiménez in January 23, 1958 the district *23 de Enero* have been know in the country for the persistence of its inhabitants in the struggles of political and social claims for better living conditions. Maybe because the combative character of the residents, the district has been seen by different governments since 1958 as a “subversive community”, “red zone”, and an area of vagrancy. However, there exists a community rich in experiences about communal organisation. Political awareness among people has thus, allowed many of its inhabitants to acquired a critical perspective throughout the most difficult times of uncertainty, political and social debates which Venezuela has suffered during the second half of the 20th Century.

The *23 de Enero* has an array of people, including honest, responsible and professional individuals; it also has a variety of cultures and music. The area is characterized by different communities of social struggle such as: Abrebrecha Bolivarian Circle, Foundation Simón Bolívar, Revolutionary Movement Tupamaro, Community Block 17, the Working Group La Piedrita, Muralist Brigade Ernesto Guevara de la Serna, Abrebrecha Muralist Brigade, Cultural Coordinator Simon Bolívar among others. Most of these groups still continue on their activities, but others have disappeared. The area also counts with two communal radio channels, “Al Son” (To the rhythm) and “Combative and Libertaria” (Combative and Libertarian). Both were created to make local voice heard, giving space to people’s concerns, opinions and suggestions.

Around the residential buildings constructed in 1950, low-income neighbourhoods came into existence. The houses and entire infrastructure have been planned and constructed by local people, and most often by the men of families. Unlike the ‘regular’ city dweller

who depends upon the central city for income and commercial entertainment, the low-income communities in the *23 de Enero* survive by doing things themselves, their skills are highly valuable for sustaining their families. House-by-house were built by ordinary people, bringing along the construction of pedestrian way outs and roads. However, it is difficult to find professional designers or architects living in low-income communities.

The government of President Chávez has implemented different Misiones (Missions) which consist of free education, free health care systems, urban renewal projects and cultural activities among others. Currently, the area also counts with the Committee of Urban Land, Communal Councils and the Technical Board of Water. Following I briefly illustrate some of the projects and initiatives created by two communities in *23 de Enero* after the law of community councils was decreed in 2009.

COMMUNAL COUNCIL SIERRA MAESTRA

Often, community councils need to have a common space where different activities and meetings can take place. Since the Communal Council of Sierra Maestra did not find a proper house in the neighbourhood they came up with the idea of building a two-floor house above the main street (see figure 1). Since the communal council of Sierra Maestra was not sure about the viability of the idea, they turned to governmental bodies for assistance. They either count with local engineers, architects, designers or the like that could provide professional help. After some months the house was built, on the first floor lays the common space and office for the communal council’s activities. The second floor was allocated for the economical development of the community and individuals, counting with six professional sewing machines (see figure 2). Here, the community will receive training courses for learning how to sew, and assistance from the government to learn social, cultural and economical strategies regarding the products and services they can offer to other people, companies and communities.

Figure 1. Communal council house designed by the communal council of Sierra Maestra, 23 de Enero. Caracas, 2012.

Figure 2. Communal council house. Sewing machines on second floor. 23 de Enero. Caracas, 2012.

So far, the community also counts with an Infocentro (infocentre) which provides computer training (running only the operating system Linux) by people from the same community and unlimited broadband internet access free of charge. The Infocentro is the common place where locals attend, serving also students for doing their homework. The Infocentro is the result of a partnership between the Ministry of Science and Technology and the local communities. The ministry provides the materials, logistical support and computers, and the community built the centre and chose the staff. Five hundred similar Infocentros have been opened in low-income neighbourhoods.

COMMUNAL COUNCIL LA PIEDRITA

La Piedrita is a radical revolutionary collective founded 26 years ago. The first contact with the current government for obtaining community support was through Misión Tricolor (Tricolor Mission) which

subsidy families for the renovation of their houses. This opened a new set of initiatives for the development of the neighbourhood. The area was cleaned up and partly regenerated. Currently, La Piedrita counts with animals, part of them are pets and others are utilized for local food production, including chickens, sheep, quails and a fishpond harvest (see figures 3 and 4).

La Piedrita also have a metal and wood workshop where the skill knowledge is handed out to younger generations through training course. The community also produces adobe to supply internal doings and sell in reasonable price to other communities, companies and individuals. In 2009 the communal council of La Piedrita requested the government machinery to make blocks, and thus the presidential commission went over to inspect the quality of the space and evaluate the conditions for implementing the block factory (see figure 5). The machinery and materials were donated together with a training course for locals who will operate it. It is the first communal council in Venezuela that produces blocks. Moreover, the community counts with a popular kitchen and dining room targeted to homeless people, individuals working for the community, children and seniors. Resources of various kinds are provided by the government initiatives. For instance, the food is bought in markets owned by the state where prices are significantly low. La Piedrita also take advantage of their own food production.

Figure 3. Communal council La Piedrita. Local food production: chicken. 23 de Enero. Caracas, 2012.

Figure 4. Communal council La Piedrita. Fish pond harvest. 23 de Enero. Caracas, 2012.

Figure 5. Communal council La Piedrita. Local workers building extension for block production. 23 de Enero. Caracas, 2012. discussion

DISCUSSION

Designing for services, for communities, and for social realities and taking approaches on co-creation, co-design, empathic and participatory design seem to be far away from the educational curricula of the design field in Venezuela. However, I have briefly illustrated various cases that implicitly comprise co-design, co-creation, and the design of services and communities with and for people. The only difference is that the invention happens by non-designers; and such notions and concepts carry rather another vocabulary and expression by local people. Co-design, empathic and participatory approaches based on “making”, toolkits, are out of practice, and perhaps demand, within these developing communities. Instead, more informal meetings and talks take place for idea creation and less material is used. ‘Ordinary’ people in

low-income neighbourhoods are designers by nature, as we all are. However, when politic and government intervention give the opportunity for them to shine, incredible design ideas come into existence; and real communities can flourish. Their process of idea creation is simple and ordinary, it is based on traditional discussion and it focuses on its real context and lives. However, the right elements to make a community function are based on good communication, common understanding of priorities and outreach, and the establishment of norms based on sharing, participation and cooperation.

On one hand, design professionals are out of demand in many self-organized low-income communities in the current Venezuela. They have hardly needed the expertise of a professional designer. In the communal council Sierra Maestra, engineers were only required to evaluate the viability of the idea created by the community. On the other hand, La Piedrita disregards professional because they know too much of theory and little of practice.

It seems essential to highlight the great amount of non-intentional designers, especially in low-income areas. The necessity to survive and struggle in a society of political, racial, economical and cultural conflicts makes people strong, and helps them to invent and make their living environment according to their views. They usually learn and make things to overcome bad conditions of life without the need to study three or five years in an institution. They learn by doing and they study, directly or indirectly, the meaning and construction of everyday life in communities until they become experts in running their own community and in building the necessary infrastructure to embrace local culture and local development.

An extensive amount of land in the area of 23 de Enero in Caracas became urbanizations and neighbourhoods of poor people without the utilization of architects, designers or engineers. People, without hardly any professional training, built houses and urbanizations for the sake of needs, desires and know-how. Thus, people are highly creative and practical in the poor and rural areas of Venezuela. Communal councils and organized communities in the

country are not only creative communities but also radical people who struggle for social and economic change. The current politic of the country is perhaps, a facilitator to drive this change. It seems that participatory design and co-creation have surprisingly reached a population who has struggled for better living conditions.

Organized communities and the inventions created in low-income community neighbourhoods have lot to offer to design, as they inherently appropriate and adapt concepts and practices utilized in design. For instance, attitudes that drive social change, social well-being and sustainability. Local designers and the design field in Venezuela can fruitfully take advantage of the current politic intervention to focus on design that is really needed in the country, as it is design for communities and services. Moreover, developing countries should not follow the exact track of the so-called, developed countries. Developing countries can take a shortcut in the development process of design practice and research, where real design for communities and social well-being is reached. They should invent and re-create their own design approaches based on their everyday interactions and culture, which sometimes seem to be more rich, diverse and profound than in developed countries.

Finally, design thinking, the role of design and designers as drivers of change, and vehicles of communication seem to be an important standpoint to take in the current shift of the Venezuelan society. Design interventions in developing communities and community councils can facilitate fruitful dynamics and understandings between individuals in those communities. Also, design intervention can provide special tools and design processes to map ideas and common understandings within communities offering them an accurate plan of implementation.

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